

EUPHRESKO Communication Strategy

Audience: EUPHRESKO Participants (Project Partners, Network Management Group, Governing Board and Observers)

Aim: To ensure effective communication between Project Partners in matters relating to the management and coordination activities of EUPHRESKO; to ensure effective strategic oversight of the Project; keep observers informed of progress and actively engaged.

- EUPHRESKO website (secure area): contains project management and WP-related documents and minutes of meetings.
- Project Office – dedicated EUPHRESKO email address for central contact point.
- Meetings: 6-monthly Project meetings where all Project Partners attend (Observers invited as appropriate, but not funded); 6-monthly Network Management Group (NMG) meetings; annual Governing Board (GB) meetings.
- EUPHRESKO newsletter - all Project Partners, Observer Partners, GB members to automatically receive e-newsletter alerts.
- Observers funded from the Project to attend final dissemination conference.

Audience: European Commission (DG-Research), other ERA-Nets, EU-funded projects and other EU initiatives

Aim: To ensure effective communication between EUPHRESKO and the Commission in all matters relating to the EUPHRESKO. To ensure EUPHRESKO learns from the experiences of other ERA-Nets; to ensure linkages with other appropriate EU projects and initiatives.

- Reports to the EUPHRESKO Commission desk officer: Quarterly reports of progress against milestones and deliverables; Project Office as central point of contact; invite Commission representative to attend 6-monthly Project and/or GB meetings.
- Representatives of EUPHRESKO to attend Commission-held workshops/meetings relevant to ERA-Nets; invite representatives of other ERA-Nets to give presentations at appropriate 6-monthly project meetings; obtain relevant documents from other ERA-Nets to develop processes, instruments and tools for EUPHRESKO.
- Provide comments to the Technology Platforms as appropriate; also SCAR (Standing Committee of Agricultural Research), KBBE (knowledge-based bioeconomy) networks and ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures)
- EUPHRESKO to consider links to other EU-funded Projects, e.g. Networks of Excellence (current link with ENDURE), COST Actions, PHARE Projects, etc.

Audience: European Plant Health Policy Bodies (e.g. EPPO; EC DG SANCO; EFSA-PHP; COPHS; SCPH)

Aim: To promote the activities of EUPHRESKO in a policy context and allow policy makers/bodies to have input into EUPHRESKO research agendas to better underpin European phytosanitary policy.

- Invite members of the ‘virtual’ Expert Advisory Group (EPPO; EFSA-PHP; DG SANCO) to provide comments to the Governing Board, or to attend GB meetings as appropriate; invite comment from EAG on key project documents/issues;; continue to invite COPA-COGECA to participate in the EAG, but to consider alternative ways to engage non-governmental ‘industry’ stakeholders, e.g. establish a small ‘virtual’ group of national ‘industry’ representative bodies; EPPO Diagnostic Panel meetings to have a standing ‘EUPHRESKO’ agenda item.

- Coordinator to produce updates for 6-monthly COPHS (EU Council working Party of Chief Officers of Plant Health Services) meetings and to present reports in person as appropriate; COPHS national representatives to be encouraged to continue to lobby their national/regional phytosanitary funding bodies to support EUPHRESKO pilot projects and future activities; comments from the COPHS to feed back to GB.
- Engagement as appropriate with Plant Health Standing Committee (SCPH) on future agendas (in discussion with, or at the invitation of, DG SANCO).

Audience: International Plant Health Bodies or Interest Groups

Aim: To raise awareness of the aims, objectives and activities of EUPHRESKO and to start to develop international linkages related to plant health research.

- Communication with FAO-IPPC-secretariat over EUPHRESKO aims for European research coordination and future linkages more internationally
- Communication/dissemination activities at international conferences to promote EUPHRESKO's activities, e.g. a stand at ICPP 2008 (International Congress of Plant Pathology)
- E-newsletters and Project website

Audience: European Researchers/Scientists and 'Industry' Stakeholders

Aim: To raise awareness of the aims, objectives and activities of EUPHRESKO, to engage with these researcher and 'industry' stakeholders in developing policy-led research agendas.

- EUPHRESKO website – mailing list of people identified by Partners – encourage registering for e-newsletter alerts; publication of calls on Project website.
- EUPHRESKO E-newsletters
- EUPHRESKO leaflet – Partners to distribute at phytosanitary-related conferences/meetings.
- Press releases, articles and web-links – EUPHRESKO links on Partner's websites and use of EUPHRESKO Press Releases; national publicity by Partners through popular press articles etc.
- Final dissemination conference – funds provided by the Project to invite representatives from these organisations to attend.
- Engage with other scientific plant health fora, e.g. European Mycological Network, and networks being considered for viruses, bacteria etc.; presentations about EUPHRESKO by Partners who are part of these Networks and attend their meetings.
- Publicise EUPHRESKO through the EUROPA/CORDIS website and through the EPPO website.
- Database of research providers and 'industry' stakeholders identified by Partners.